

Coupling Achiral and Chiral Chromatography for Efficient Separation of Enantiomeric Mixtures

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ABSTRACT: Chiral chromatography (CCh) is often a cost driver in the large-scale separation of enantiomers. To improve the economics of the separation process, we developed the concept of coupling CCh with achiral chromatography (ACh). In this concept, the CCh step is used to enrich the enantiomeric mixture with the target enantiomer, while in the ACh step, the enriched mixture is separated to obtain the product with a desired purity. The ACh separation is driven by the phenomenon of self-disproportionation of enantiomers (SDE), which relies on formation of homochiral and heterochiral associates that can be separated in an achiral environment, whereas the CCh separation occurs in the presence of a chiral stationary phase (CSP). The coupled ACh-CCh process is operated in a cyclic mode for which cyclic steady state is attained. To demonstrate the concept of the process and develop a generic methodology for its design, a model mixture consisting of enantiomers of methyl *p*-tolyl sulfoxide was used, with *S*-*p*-tolyl sulfoxide as the target enantiomer. For both ACh and CCh, the influence of the operating variables, including mobile phase composition, loading density, and enantiomeric excess (ee) of the feed mixture, on the separation performance was examined. On the basis of the experimental data, a dynamic model was formulated, calibrated, and used to support the process design and assess the performance of both the standalone ACh and CCh as well as their coupling in various configurations. The amount of product obtained in a single cycle of ACh-CCh was markedly higher compared to that obtained in the standalone CCh, which provided the benefit of reducing consumption of the costly CSP. This benefit was enhanced with increasing ee of the feed mixture. For example, for racemic mixtures, the mass of the product per cycle of ACh-CCh was 1.5 times higher, for mixtures with ee = 70% it was 4 times higher, and for mixtures with ee = 85% it was 5.7 times higher compared to the standalone CCh. Furthermore, for mixtures with a high ee, a marked improvement in process productivity was obtained, e.g., for mixtures with ee = 70%, the productivity of ACh-CCh was twice higher, for ee = 85% it was 2.5 times higher compared to the standalone CCh.

1. INTRODUCTION

Currently, chiral drugs are on the cutting edge of the pharmaceutical industry and account for more than 70% of the drug market.¹ Since 1992, when the Food and Drug Administration (FDA) issued a regulatory preference to bring a single enantiomer to the market,² the trend in chiral drug discovery has evolved toward the development of single enantiomer drugs. Individual enantiomers of chiral drugs may differ in biological activity, pharmacology, toxicology, pharmacokinetics, and metabolism. Usually, only one enantiomer provides the desired therapeutic effect, while another enantiomer may be inactive, less active or in some cases may cause adverse effects.^{3,4} Therefore, the manufacturing of chiral drugs composed of a single enantiomer allows the improvement of the drug safety, efficacy, and cost-effectiveness of the production process. In addition to the development of a new

chiral drug into a therapy, the 'chiral switch' strategy has appeared in which the existing racemate is switched to the target optical isomer.^{5–9}

Enantiopure chiral compounds are not only desirable by the pharmaceutical industry; they have a number of potential applications in various fields, including DNA or drug delivery, optics, electronics, photonics, catalysis, nanotechnology, and biosensing.^{10,11} Interest in the production of pure enantiomers extends also to the production of food and agrochemicals.^{12,13}

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This indicates that there is an urgent need to develop new cost-effective techniques for bringing pure enantiomers to market.

Currently, single enantiomers are produced through asymmetric or symmetric synthesis.^{14–18} Symmetric synthesis does not require a chiral environment; it provides a racemic mixture of two enantiomers, which, however, has to be further resolved in the presence of a chiral selector. Asymmetric synthesis is the most straightforward; therefore, increasing efforts are made to develop selective chiral reagents and catalysts that enable precise synthesis of chiral substances.^{19–21} Nevertheless, asymmetric synthesis rarely provides a single enantiomer, but rather a mixture of enantiomers with a certain enantiomeric excess (ee). The postsynthesis mixture has to be further separated in the presence of a chiral selector to acquire a single enantiomer with a proper purity level.

In large-scale applications, chiral chromatography (CCh) or diastereoisomeric crystallization are generally used for chiral resolution.^{22–24} Diastereoisomeric crystallization is considered a straightforward and effective method, provided that a suitable chiral resolving agent is available. However, the complexity of the crystallization thermodynamics of diastereomeric mixtures makes the identification of an efficient resolving agent challenging or even in many cases impossible.²⁵ In contrast, CCh can be used for the separation of a wide variety of chiral compounds, regardless of the state of matter in which they occur or the underlying thermodynamics of phase equilibrium. The process design is facilitated by the easy commercial availability of various types of chiral stationary phases (CSPs). Therefore, it is frequently used for the industrial separation of enantiomeric mixtures, either as an alternative to diastereomeric crystallization or as the only possible option. However, the high price of CSPs, along with their relatively low mechanical stability and limited binding capacity, renders CChs a significant cost driver and a bottleneck in the manufacturing of enantiomers. To reduce manufacturing costs, CCh can be in some cases replaced by cheap achiral chromatography (ACh) based on plane silica adsorbents. The low cost of the silica adsorbent and its high mechanical stability enable the chromatographic columns to be operated at high flow rates and thus at high throughput, which makes ACh an attractive alternative to CCh.

The separation of enantiomers by ACh is based on the formation of homochiral and heterochiral associates of the enantiomers, which differ in adsorption properties in nonracemic mixtures. This phenomenon, termed self-disproportionation of enantiomers (SDE),²⁶ enables the isolation of the target enantiomer present in excess in the nonracemic mixture. SDE has been reported to occur for chiral compounds containing so-called SDE-phoric groups, including sulfoxides, CF₃-derived substances, amides, carboxylic acids, amino acids, dipeptide derivatives, alcohols, phenols, esters, heterocycles, whose presence triggers the mutual interactions of enantiomers via hydrogen bonding or dipole–dipole interactions.^{26–35} This long list of SDE-phoric groups implies that chiral separation by ACh is not limited to highly specific or rare cases, but it is applicable to a wide variety of compounds.

In recent studies, a mathematical model was formulated for the quantitative description of SDE-driven ACh separation and the determination of the influence of operating variables on the extent of the SDE effect.^{36,37} Furthermore, the possibility of performing continuous SDE-driven ACh separations based on the simulated moving bed separation was demonstrated.³⁸

In this study, we developed a model-assisted procedure for the design of SDE-driven ACh and its coupling with a CCh

operating in a cyclic mode. In this approach, standalone ACh is intended to be used instead of expensive CCh to reduce separation costs for postsynthesis enantiomeric mixtures with a high ee, but it is insufficiently high to meet the desired level of product purity. In turn, the coupled ACh-CCh process can be used to minimize the usage of CSPs in the CCh step for mixtures with a low ee, for which the separation efficiency of standalone ACh is insufficient, or for racemates, for which separation by standalone ACh is not possible.

To establish a general theoretical background for the design of the cyclic ACh-CCh process, a dynamic model was formulated and calibrated for model mixtures of methyl *p*-tolyl sulfoxide enantiomers, with the *S*-enantiomer as the target product. A model-assisted systematic study was performed to evaluate the separation performance of standalone ACh and CCh and their coupling as a function of various operating variables, including mobile phase composition, column loading density, ee of the feed mixture, and flow configuration in different flowsheet schemes.

2. THEORY

2.1. Dynamic Model. To simulate chromatographic band profiles, the equilibrium-dispersive (ED) model was used. The model was expressed by the following differential mass balance equation³⁹

$$\frac{\partial C_i}{\partial t} + \frac{u}{\varepsilon_t} \frac{\partial C_i}{\partial x} + F \frac{\partial q_{\text{tot},i}^*}{\partial t} = D_{L,a} \frac{\partial^2 C_i}{\partial x^2} \quad (1)$$

where $q_{\text{tot},i}^*$ is the equilibrium concentration of the enantiomer i (i denotes the *S* or *R* enantiomer) in the adsorbed phase, in mg per mL of the solid matrix ($\text{mg mL}_{\text{matrix}}^{-1}$) given by the isotherm eq (eq 8 or eq 9), C_i (mg mL^{-1}) is the corresponding liquid phase concentration, t (s), x (m) are the time and spatial coordinates, respectively, u (m s^{-1}) refers the superficial velocity, $D_{L,a}$ ($\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$) is the apparent dispersion coefficient, F is the phase ratio: $F = (1 - \varepsilon_t)/\varepsilon_t$, ε_t is the packed bed porosity.

The model is combined with the boundary conditions corresponding to loading at the column inlet a rectangular pulse of the feed sample with the concentration $C_{i,F}$ at $t > 0$

$$C_{i,\text{inlet}}(x = 0, t) = \begin{cases} C_{i,F} & \text{for } t \in [0, t_{\text{load}}] \\ 0 & \text{for } t > t_{\text{load}} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where t_{load} is the loading time of the feed mixture.

For the concentration profile at the column outlet at $t > 0$, it holds

$$\frac{\partial C_i(t, x = L)}{\partial x} = 0 \quad (3)$$

where L is the column length.

The initial conditions ($t = 0$) correspond to the column free of the feed components.

The apparent dispersion coefficient, $D_{L,a}$, is given by the following equation

$$D_{L,a} = \frac{Lu}{2N\varepsilon_t} = \frac{\text{HETP}u}{2\varepsilon_t} \quad (4)$$

where N is the plate number that corresponds to the column efficiency, $\text{HETP} = L/N$, HETP is a function of the mobile phase velocity, which is quantified by the van Deemter equation.³⁹

Figure 1. Cartoon representation of SDE-driven adsorption on an achiral adsorbent, where A^* is an active site on the adsorbent surface, K^I is the equilibrium constant of binding on bare surface, K_{hom}^{II} , K_{het}^{II} are the equilibrium constants of formation of homo- and hetero- associates.

Productivity, yield, and purity were used as performance indicators. Productivity, Pr , was defined as the ratio of the mass of the product, $m_{t,\text{prod}}$, i.e., the mass of the purified target enantiomer, t , acquired during a single chromatographic cycle, to the duration of the cycle, t_c , and to the column volume, V_{col}

$$Pr = \frac{m_{t,\text{prod}}}{t_c V_{\text{col}}} \quad (5)$$

The yield, Y , was defined as the ratio of the mass of the purified target enantiomer, $m_{t,\text{prod}}$, to its mass loaded into the separation unit, $m_{t,\text{load}}$

$$Y = \frac{m_{t,\text{prod}}}{m_{t,\text{load}}} 100\% \quad (6)$$

The purity of the product, Pu , was defined as the ratio of $m_{t,\text{prod}}$ to the mass of the whole product m_{prod}

$$Pu = \frac{m_{t,\text{prod}}}{m_{\text{prod}}} 100\% \quad (7)$$

The model was solved using the forward–backward scheme,⁴⁰ which allows very fast solution of the model, thus enabling the fast calibration of the model and the selection of operating conditions to optimize process performance.

2.2. Description of the Adsorption Equilibrium.

2.2.1. Adsorption Equilibrium in ACh. As mentioned above, the adsorption of enantiomers in ACh is driven by the SDE phenomenon. To quantify the process, a two-layer adsorption mechanism was assumed;^{36,37} in the first layer enantiomers are bound in a nonselective way to active sites on the bare silica surface. The adsorbed molecules provide active sites for interaction with another molecule, either of the same enantiomer or the opposite one. The corresponding reaction path is illustrated in Figure 1. At adsorption equilibrium, the total adsorption of the enantiomer i , $q_{i,\text{tot}}^*$ is the sum of the adsorbed phase concentration in both layers, which can be expressed as follows^{36,37}

$$\begin{aligned} q_{i,\text{tot}}^* &= q_i^{*I} + q_i^{*II} \\ &= \frac{q_i^m K^I C_i}{1 + K^I \sum_j C_j} + \frac{q_i^{*I} K_{\text{hom}}^{II} C_i}{1 + K_{\text{hom}}^{II} C_i + K_{\text{het}}^{II} C_j} \\ &\quad + \frac{q_j^{*I} K_{\text{het}}^{II} C_i}{1 + K_{\text{het}}^{II} C_i + K_{\text{hom}}^{II} C_j} \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

The first term on the right-hand side of eq 8 corresponds to the adsorption of the i -th enantiomer on bare silica, the second and third terms correspond to the adsorption of homochiral and

heterochiral associates, respectively, q_i^{mI} is the binding capacity in the first layer, and K^I is the corresponding equilibrium constant, which are the same for both enantiomers because of the absence of binding selectivity on bare silica; $K_i^I = K_j^I = K^I$ and $q_i^{mI} = q_j^{mI} = q^{mI}$, K_{hom}^{II} , K_{het}^{II} are the equilibrium constants of formation of homo and hetero associates, respectively. The difference between the K_{hom}^{II} , K_{het}^{II} determines the separation selectivity.

2.2.2. Adsorption Equilibrium in CCh. The adsorption of enantiomers in CCh was described using the standard competitive Langmuir isotherm model, expressed as

$$q_i^* = \frac{q_i^m K_i C_i}{1 + \sum_j K_j C_j} \quad (9)$$

where q_i^m is the binding capacity of the enantiomer i ($i = S$ or R), K_i is the equilibrium constant, and C_i is the concentration of the enantiomer i in the liquid phase.

3. EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

3.1. Equipment. The Hitachi HPLC Primade system was used to perform chromatographic experiments. The HPLC device consisted of a high-pressure quaternary pump, an autosampler, a column thermostat, an interface module, and a UV detector.

3.2. Materials. *R,S*-Methyl *p*-tolyl sulfoxide (*R,S*-MTSO) ($Pu > 99\%$), was purchased from Apollo Scientific (Bredbury, U.K.), *S*-Methyl *p*-tolyl sulfoxide (*S*-MTSO) ($Pu > 98\%$) was obtained from AmBeed (Arlington Heights), *R*-Methyl *p*-tolyl sulfoxide (*R*-MTSO) ($Pu > 99\%$) was obtained from Sigma-Aldrich (Saint Louis). Methyl *tert*-butyl ether (MTBE) and isopropyl alcohol (*i*-PrOH) of HPLC-grade purity were obtained from Honeywell (Charlotte).

For SDE-driven ACh separations, the ReproSil-Pur 60 Si silica gel column (250 mm \times 4.6 mm, 5 μm particle size) was purchased from Dr Maisch (Ammerbuch, Germany).

CCh separations and analysis of ACh and CCh effluents were performed with the CHIRALPAK IC (250 mm \times 4.6 mm, 5 μm particle size) from Daicel Corporation (Osaka, Japan).

3.3. Procedures. 3.3.1. Chromatographic Elution.

3.3.3.1. ACh Separation. The chromatographic conditions for the separation of nonracemic mixtures of the MTSO enantiomers by ACh were selected in the previous study.³⁷ The experiments were conducted isocratically with a mobile phase composed of MTBE with *i*-PrOH as the modifier. The *i*-PrOH content in the mobile phase was stepwise changed within the range of separation feasibility: $\phi_{i\text{-PrOH}} = 0, 1, 3, 10, 15\%$ v/v. The mobile phase flow rate was $Q = 1 \text{ mL min}^{-1}$.

Nonracemic mixtures of MTSO with $ee_s = 50$ or 85% and the total feed mixture concentration of $C_F = 60 \text{ mg mL}^{-1}$ were

Figure 2. Profiles of the MTSO enantiomers eluted from the ACh column for feed samples with $ee_{S,F} = 50\%$, $V_F = 0.09$ mL, $C_F = 60$ mg mL $^{-1}$, mobile phase MTBE/*i*-PrOH: $\varphi_{i\text{-PrOH}} = 10, 3, 1\%$, $Q = 1$ mL min $^{-1}$. (A) individual profiles of the enantiomers, symbols – experimental data, lines – simulations, (B) corresponding UV profiles.

loaded in volumes of $V_F = 0.09$ or 0.5 mL. Chromatographic profiles were recorded at a wavelength of 285 nm.

Individual profiles of enantiomers in the mixtures were determined by fractionation of effluent from the ACh column and subsequent offline analysis of fractions using the CCh column (Section 3.3.3.3). The volume of fractions was changed from 0.1 to 2 mL according to the pace of changes in the detector signal.

All chromatographic experiments reported in this study were carried out at a temperature of 23 °C.

3.3.3.2. CCh Separation. The mobile phase composed of MTBE and *i*-PrOH was also found to be suitable for the separation of the MTSO enantiomers by CCh. The separation was performed for various concentrations of *i*-PrOH: $\varphi_{i\text{-PrOH}} = 5, 10, 12, 15,$ and 20% v/v. The flow rate of the mobile phase was $Q = 1$ mL min $^{-1}$. Mixtures of the MTSO enantiomers with $ee_S = 0\%$ (racemate) or $ee_S = 50\%$ and total feed concentration $C_F = 60$ mg mL $^{-1}$ were loaded in volumes of $V_F = 0.05$ or 0.5 mL. Chromatographic profiles were recorded at a wavelength of 285 nm. Analysis of CCh effluent was performed according to the procedure described in Section 3.3.3.3.

3.3.3.3. Fraction Analysis. The effluent analysis of both the ACh and CCh columns was performed using the CHIRALPAK IC column with MTBE/*i*-PrOH (85:15 v/v) as the mobile phase at a flow rate $Q = 1.5$ mL min $^{-1}$. Profiles were recorded at a wavelength of 246 nm. The detection wavelength was adjusted to ensure the linearity of the detector calibration curve. The sample volume was selected in such a way that the base peak resolution was achieved.

3.3.3.4. Measurements of the Column Porosity. The column porosity was calculated on the basis of the retention time of *n*-hexane pulses in the mobile phase. The column retention times were corrected by subtracting the residence time in the extra column volumes. The total bed porosity was determined to be $\varepsilon_t = 0.704$ for the ACh column and $\varepsilon_t = 0.741$ for the CCh column.

3.3.3.5. Measurement of the Number of Theoretical Plates. The number of theoretical plates for each column was determined from the half-peak width of a small pulse ($V_F = 0.05$ mL, $C_F = 0.5$ mg mL $^{-1}$) of S-MTISO eluted from the ACh column and for S- and R-MTISO pulses eluted from the CCh column. Measurements were carried out with the highest modifier content in the mobile phase ($\varphi = 15\%$ v/v for ACh, $\varphi = 20\%$ v/v for CCh). Measurements were made for various mobile

phase flow rates in the range $Q = 1\text{--}8.3$ mL min $^{-1}$ for ACh column and $Q = 1\text{--}4$ mL min $^{-1}$; the upper limit for Q was determined for the maximum allowable pressure drop in the ACh and CCh columns, respectively.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Model Calibration. **4.1.1. Separation in the Stand-alone ACh.** To quantitatively describe the separation of MTISO enantiomers in the ACh column, the ED model (eq 1) was coupled with the isotherm eq (eq 8). The model calibration consisted of the determination of a few parameters, including the column porosity, ε_p , the apparent dispersion coefficient, $D_{a,L}$, and the isotherm coefficients: q^{ml} , K^I , K_{homo}^{II} , K_{het}^{II} .

The column porosity was determined according to the procedure described in Section 3.3.3.4. The coefficient $D_{a,L}$ was calculated from the number of theoretical plates N (eq 4). The latter was determined at a high modifier content in the mobile phase, for which the MTISO peaks took a Gaussian shape. At low modifier concentrations, peak tailing was observed, which resulted from the energetical heterogeneity of the silica adsorbent surface. Under such conditions, accurate determination of N was not possible. In general, for strongly adsorbing species, the retention dependence of $D_{L,a}$ in the ED model (eq 1) is very weak; therefore, it also depends weakly on the mobile phase composition (Supporting Information, eqs S1 and S2). However, its dependence on the mobile phase velocity cannot be neglected. An increase in the mobile phase velocity causes a decrease in the column efficiency. Therefore, the velocity dependence of $D_{L,a}$ has to be quantified and accounted for in the model. For this purpose, a series of elution experiments were performed in both ACh and CCh columns for small pulses of S-MTISO at varying mobile phase flow rates (Section 3.3.3.5). The resulting van Deemter curve was described by an empirical function (Figure S1, Supporting Information) and used to calculate $D_{L,a}$.

To determine the isotherm coefficients, the peak fitting method was used, in which the coefficient values were adjusted by an optimization procedure to obtain a best match between the model simulations and the experimental band profiles. The latter were acquired under conditions of strong isotherm nonlinearity. Each profile selected as the input data was characterized by a sharp ascending concentration front; the front of S-MTISO, which was in excess in the mixture, always

moved faster than that of the unwanted R-MTISO enantiomer, which activated displacement effect. This allowed for acquiring a pure fraction of S-MTISO preceding the R-MTISO front. The peak fitting procedure was performed for the band profiles of enantiomeric mixtures with $ee_S = 50\%$ at varying modifier concentrations in the mobile phase (Section 3.3.3.1). The retention pattern is illustrated in Figure 2A, which shows individual profiles of enantiomers along with the results of peak fitting, and in Figure 2B, in which the total UV profiles are depicted. The rear part of the UV profiles exhibits a characteristic hump that accompany retention of the later-eluted enantiomer. The presence of such a deformation of UV profiles of nonracemic mixtures is an indicator of the occurrence and extent of SDE in ACh, which facilitates optimization of operating conditions.

It can be observed that a reduction in the modifier concentration caused an enhancement in the SDE effect, which improved the separation selectivity, hence also the yield of the target S-MTISO. In general, the mobile phase with a low polarity is recommended for the SDE-driven separations, as the excess of polar solvent diminishes the SDE effect.³⁷ On the other hand, it caused an extension of the duration of the separation cycle, which reduced productivity. The retention pattern was reflected in the values of the isotherm coefficients. The equilibrium constant of binding on bare silica, K^I and the difference between the coefficients K_{homo}^{II} and K_{het}^{II} determining the separation selectivity, decreased with increasing modifier concentration, which is illustrated in Figure 3. The binding capacity for the MTISO enantiomers was found to be independent of the modifier content, consistent with observations from a previous study.³⁷

Figure 3. Dependencies of the isotherm coefficients on the modifier content in the mobile phase for ACh. Symbols – experimental data, lines – empirical functional dependencies (Table S1, Supporting Information), $q^{mI} = 63.6$ is the average value obtained for different modifier concentrations.

The values obtained were successfully verified by comparing the model predictions with the experimental profiles of enantiomeric mixtures recorded under different ee_S and loading conditions (Figure S2, Supporting Information).

4.1.2. CCh Separation. The calibration of the dynamic model of the CCh column was performed in a way similar to that described above for the ACh column. To determine the mobile phase dependence of $D_{L,a}$, the van Deemter curve was generated

and quantified by an empirical function, which is demonstrated in Figure S1 in Supporting Information.

Four isotherm coefficients, q_S^m , q_R^m , K_S , K_R were determined using the peak fitting method. The basis of the peak fitting were the band profiles of the MTISO enantiomers in racemic mixtures ($ee_{S,F} = 0\%$) recorded at varying concentrations of the modifier in the mobile phase (3.3.3.2). For the CCh system used, the S-MTISO enantiomer was eluted from the CCh column before R-MTISO. The predictability of the model was verified by comparing the predictions with the experimental profiles recorded under different ee_S and loading conditions (Figure S2, Supporting Information).

An illustration of the retention pattern of the MTISO enantiomers in the CCh column and the results of peak fitting is depicted in Figure 4. The dependence of the isotherm parameters on the modifier concentration in the mobile phase is illustrated in Figure 5. The corresponding empirical functional dependencies are given in Table S2 in Supporting Information. It can be observed that both the equilibrium constants K_R and K_S decrease with increasing modifier concentration in the mobile phase. The adsorption capacities of the enantiomers S-MTISO, q_S^m , and R-MTISO, q_R^m , were different and exhibited opposite trends with respect to the modifier content; q_S^m decreased while q_R^m increased with increasing modifier concentration. As a result, the separation selectivity decreased with increasing modifier content, particularly for modifier concentrations greater than approximately 12% (v/v).

Figure 4. Individual profiles of the MTISO enantiomers eluted from the CCh column for feed samples with $ee_{S,F} = 0\%$, $V_F = 0.05$ mL, $C_F = 50$ mg mL⁻¹, mobile phase MTBE/*i*-PrOH: $\phi_{i-PrOH} = 20, 15, 10\%$. Symbols – experimental data, lines – simulations.

4.2. Separation Performance of the Standalone ACh and the Standalone CCh.

4.2.1. Separation Performance of the Standalone ACh. The dynamic model was used for systematic analysis of the separation performance of the MTISO enantiomers by ACh. The model was solved for incremental changes in the process variables within the range of separation feasibility, i.e., for the modifier concentration $\phi = 1, 2, 3, 5,$ and 10% v/v and the loading density L_d (mass of enantiomers loaded per the column volume) changed from 3.6 to 14.5 mg mL⁻¹ (loading volume V_F changed from 0.25 to 1 mL). The values of the isotherm coefficients and the coefficient $D_{L,a}$ were implemented using proper functional dependencies on

Figure 5. Dependencies of the isotherm coefficients on the modifier content in the mobile phase for CCh. Symbols – experimental data, lines – empirical functional dependencies (Table S2, Supporting Information).

the modifier concentration and flow rates, respectively (Table S1 and Figure S1, Supporting Information).

The SDE effect enhances with increasing concentration of enantiomers as a result of the acceleration of the association rate.^{36,37} Therefore, the loading concentration was set to its maximum level corresponding to the solubility of MTSO enantiomers in the mobile phase, i.e., $C_F = 60 \text{ mg mL}^{-1}$. Therefore, changes in mass loading were defined by changes in loading volume. The simulations were repeated for different levels of ee_S in the feed mixture; $ee_{S,F} = 30, 50, 70, 85\%$. The single cycle time, t_c in eq 5 was defined as the elution time of the separated mixture in cyclic steady state, as illustrated in Figure 6.

For each simulation run, the band profiles of the enantiomers were numerically integrated. Yield (Y), productivity (Pr) and purity (Pu) of the product acquired in the first eluting fraction were calculated according to eqs 5–7. The fraction of the S-

Figure 6. Illustration of the chromatographic cycles and cut times of the effluent fractions of the ACh column (feed mixture with $ee_S = 85\%$). F1 – product fraction with the target enantiomer od purity of 99%, F2 – unresolved fraction. The cycle time: $t_c = t_e - t_s$, where t_s is the start of the collection of F1, t_e is the end of the collection of F2. The t_e and t_s were determined by the threshold concentration $C_{\text{thresh},i} = C_{F,i}/1000$, $i = S$ or R.

MTSO enantiomer that fulfilled purity of $Pu \geq 99\%$ was accepted as the separation product.

The simulation results were used to generate contour graphs, which visualize the relationship between the performance indicators Pr and Y and the operating variables, i.e., the modifier concentration, φ , and the mass loading density, L_d , at various $ee_{S,F}$ levels.

An illustration of the contour graphs calculated for two selected $ee_{S,F}$; $ee_{S,F} = 30\%$ and $ee_{S,F} = 70\%$ and a selected flow rate $Q = 4 \text{ mL min}^{-1}$ is presented in Figure 7A–D. The relationships between Pr and Y quantified for different φ and $ee_{S,F}$ are illustrated as the Pareto plots in Figure 7E,F. The Pareto plots consist of two branches connected by a maximum Pr . For the ascending branch, Pr and Y are cooperative, i.e., increasing in Y induces an improvement in Pr , since the mass of the product collected increases (eqs 5 and 6). For the descending branch, Y and Pr are conflicting; increasing demand for Y necessitates a reduction in either the loading density or in the modifier content, both of which result in decrease in Pr . The separation of enantiomers was the most challenging at the lowest $ee_{S,F}$ used for the analysis, i.e., $ee_{S,F} = 30\%$. Therefore, in this case maximum productivity was achieved for a low modifier concentration, i.e., $\varphi = 1\% \text{ v/v}$, whereas for the mixtures with $ee_S \geq 50\%$, it was achieved for $\varphi = 5\% \text{ v/v}$. Exemplary graphs are shown in Figure 7E,7F.

Changes in the mobile phase flow rate caused changes in the process performance, i.e., for the whole range investigated, a decrease in the flow rate triggered a decrease in productivity due to an extension of the duration of the chromatographic cycle (eq 5), and an increase in yield due to an improvement in the column efficiency. However, the choice of the optimum modifier concentration was not affected by the flow rate (e.g., Figure S3, Supporting Information).

The contour graphs and the Pareto plots can guide the selection of operating conditions for the standalone ACh process to trade off yield and productivity requirements.

4.2.2. Performance of the Standalone CCh. Analysis of the separation performance of the standalone CCh was also performed for enantiomeric mixtures of different $ee_{S,F}$; $ee_{S,F} = 0, 30, 50, 70, 85\%$. The modifier content in the mobile phase was incrementally changed within the range of 5 to 15% v/v ($\varphi = 5, 7, 10, 12, 15\% \text{ v/v}$) and the loading density varied from $L_d = 0.4$ to $10 \text{ mg mL}^{-1}_{\text{col}}$, which corresponded to changes in loading volume from 0.03 to 0.7 mL. The loading concentration was set according to the solubility limit, similarly as for ACh, i.e., $C_F = 60 \text{ mg mL}^{-1}$. The constraint for the purity of the product was also set at the level of $Pu \geq 99\%$.

Figure 8 illustrates the changes in Pr and Y as functions of L_d and φ for selected $ee_{S,F}$ levels ($ee_{S,F} = 30$ and 70%) at $Pu = 99\%$. The results of the calculation are demonstrated for the flow rate $Q = 4 \text{ mL min}^{-1}$ that was a maximum level due to the pressure limit of the CCh column.

It corresponded to the shortest cycle time, t_c (eq 5), for which the highest productivity was reached. The contour plots of Pr and Y are presented in Figure 8A–D, and the Pareto plots for $\varphi = 5, 10$, and $15\% \text{ v/v}$ are shown in Figure 8E,F. The maximum of Pr was achieved at $\varphi = 10\%$, regardless of ee_S of the feed mixture and the fraction eluting from the CCh column (see, e.g., Figure 7E,F, and S4 in Supporting Information).

4.3. Coupling of Achiral and Chiral Chromatography.

4.3.1. Concept of the ACh–CCh Coupling. Two flowsheet schemes for the ACh–CCh coupling were considered, which are depicted in Figure 9.

Figure 7. Illustration of the ACh separation performance for the product purity $Pu = 99\%$ (eq 7) at $Q = 4$ mL min⁻¹. (A–D) dependence of Pr (left-hand side) and Y (right-hand side) on the loading density, L_d (as a gram of enantiomers in the feed per liter of column volume) and the modifier content φ , for $ee_{S,F} = 30\%$ (A, B), and $ee_{S,F} = 70\%$ (C, D), (E, F) illustration of the corresponding Pareto plots for the selected $\varphi = 1, 3$, and 5% v/v; the lines guide the eye.

In the scheme 1, a nonracemic mixture of enantiomers, potentially resulting from an asymmetric synthesis, is loaded into the ACh column with a maximum concentration possible because of the solubility limit in the mobile phase. The mixture is separated into two fractions: the less retained, $F1_{ACh}$, which contains the pure product (*S*-MTSO) and the more retained, $F2_{ACh}$, which contains a mixture of both enantiomers. The latter is subjected to evaporation to concentrate the mixture up to the desired level and to adjust the composition of the mobile phase and loaded into the CCh column. The CCh column is destined to enrich enantiomeric mixtures in the effluent fraction, $F1_{CCh}$, up to ee_s corresponding to the feed mixture entering the ACh column. The fraction $F1_{CCh}$ is subjected to evaporation to adjust

the concentration of the mixture and the composition of the mobile phase, then mixed with a fresh portion of the feed and recycled to the ACh column, which closes the cycle. The fraction $F2_{CCh}$ that contains an excess of the undesired enantiomer *R*-MTSO is the waste from the process. The application of the scheme 1, in which the feed is directed to the ACh column, is restricted to mixtures with $ee_s > 0$, as ACh cannot be used to separate racemic mixtures.

In the scheme 2, the feed is mixed with the unresolved fraction leaving the ACh column, $F2_{ACh}$, and processed in the CCh column, which provides the fraction $F1_{CCh}$ enriched with the target enantiomer up to $ee_{S,F1CCh}$. The level of $ee_{S,F1CCh}$ is a process variable, which can be adjusted to optimize the

Figure 8. Illustration of the performance of the CCh separation for the purity of the product $Pu = 99\%$, flow rate $Q = 4 \text{ mL min}^{-1}$. (A–D) dependence of Pr and Y on L_d and φ for $ee_{S,F} = 30\%$ (A, B), and $ee_{S,F} = 70\%$ (C, D), (E, F) illustration of the corresponding Pareto plots for selected $\varphi = 5, 10, 15\%$ v/v. The lines guide the eye.

Figure 9. Flow diagram for the ACh-CCh coupling. In the scheme 1 the feed is loaded into the ACh column, in the scheme 2 the feed is loaded into the CCh column.

separation efficiency of the ACh-CCh coupling. After evaporation, the $F1_{CCh}$ fraction is fed into the ACh column to obtain the pure product in the $F1_{Ach}$ fraction, whereas the $F2_{CCh}$

fraction enriched with the undesired enantiomer is the waste from the process. The entire cycle is completed when the $F2_{Ach}$ fraction eluting from the ACh column is combined with fresh

feed and reintroduced into the CCh column. The scheme 2 can be used for enantiomeric mixtures with any ee, including racemic mixtures.

4.3.2. Evaluation of the Separation Performance of ACh-CCh. The model simulations were used to evaluate the separation performance of both ACh-CCh schemes with respect to Pr for the purity demand arbitrarily set at the level of $Pu \geq 99\%$, and minimum yield set at the level of $Y \geq 90\%$. The constraint of $Y \geq 90\%$ could be fulfilled only in the CCh step in the ACh-CCh coupling. The simulations were performed for different $ee_{S,F}$ levels; $ee_{S,F} = 30, 50, 70,$ and 85% .

The flow rate in CCh was set at the maximum allowed level, i.e., $Q_{CCh} = 4 \text{ mL min}^{-1}$, which, as mentioned above, corresponded to the maximum Pr . The Pareto plots generated for the standalone CCh were used to select the modifier content for the CCh step in the ACh-CCh coupling, for which the maximum Pr was achieved at $Y \geq 90\%$. As mentioned above, it corresponded to $\varphi_{CCh} = 10\%$, regardless of $ee_{S,F}$, (e.g., Figure 8). In this case, CCh, which was the cost driver of the separation, could operate under optimal conditions with respect of the flow rate and the modifier concentration.

The modifier concentration in the ACh step was also selected on the basis of the Pareto plots generated for the standalone ACh (Figure 7); for $ee_{S,F} = 30\%$, the modifier content was set at the level of $\varphi_{ACh} = 1\% \text{ v/v}$, whereas for $ee_{S,F} \geq 50\%$, at the level of $\varphi_{ACh} = 5\% \text{ v/v}$. The flow rate, Q_{ACh} , and the loading density, L_d , were adjusted to synchronize ACh with CCh, i.e., so that the mass of enantiomers exchanged between ACh and CCh could be separated in the same cycle duration (t_c). This approach prevented the accumulation of the mixture to be processed between ACh and CCh and allowed the establishment of cyclic steady state.

For the scheme 1, the optimization of Pr in the ACh-CCh system was initiated at L_d corresponding to the maximum Pr on the Pareto plot at the specified $ee_{S,F}$ and the selected modifier concentration. The flow rate in the initial run was set to $Q_{ACh} = 4 \text{ mL min}^{-1}$. The optimization of the ACh-CCh separation productivity was carried out according to the algorithm depicted in Figure 10. The simulations were initially repeated in the internal loop with simultaneous adjustment of Q_{ACh} , until the difference between the duration of the individual chromatographic cycle of the ACh and CCh columns fell below a specified acceptance criterion: $\Delta t_{c,ACh-CCh} = \frac{|t_{c,ACh} - t_{c,CCh}|}{t_{c,CCh}} 100\% < \delta$ and until the cyclic steady state (CSS) was attained, i.e., the relative difference in the performance indicators Pr and Y between consecutive cycles changed less than σ . Both values of δ and σ were set at 0.5% . The upper limit for Q_{ACh} was set at 8.3 mL min^{-1} , which corresponded to the allowable pressure drop for the ACh column. Subsequently, the calculations were repeated in the middle loop, in which L_d was adjusted until the constraint $Y \geq 90\%$ was met, and then in the external loop until the maximum Pr was achieved. As a result, the algorithm optimized Pr with Q_{ACh} and $L_{d,ACh}$ as decision variables subject to the following constraints: $Pu \geq 99\%$, $Y \geq 90\%$, $\delta < 0.5\%$, $\sigma < 0.5\%$.

The results of the simulations are summarized in Table 1, which presents the values Y , Pr , and the mass of the product obtained in a single chromatographic cycle, $m_{t,prod}$. Regardless of the $ee_{S,F}$ level, the maximum Pr corresponded to a very high Y level, i.e., $Y \geq 99\%$. The performance indicators obtained were compared to those calculated for the standalone CCh at the same yield. It is evident that ACh-CCh outperformed the standalone CCh with respect to both Pr and $m_{t,prod}$. The gain in

Figure 10. Calculation algorithm to optimize productivity in ACh-CCh. For the scheme 1: A denotes the ACh column and B denotes the CCh column, outA denotes the product fraction, outB is waste fraction, L_d is the loading density for the corresponding columns, $x_{i,Fk}$ is the mass ratio of the i -th enantiomer of the late eluting fraction and $x_{i,Fj}$ is the mass of the early eluting fraction, for the scheme 2: the opposite holds. In the scheme 2 the calculation cycle was additionally repeated for different levels of ee_{FICCh} .

Pr was limited by the constraint $\Delta t_{c,ACh-CCh} < \delta$, which was forced by necessity of synchronizing the separation time in both columns. Therefore, the ACh column in the coupling operated under suboptimal conditions. The gain in $m_{t,prod}$ corresponds to the reduction in the number of cycles necessary to obtain the desired mass of the product in relation to the standalone CCh. The improvement in process performance was significantly enhanced with increasing enantiomeric excess in the feed mixture; increase in $ee_{S,F}$ causes the difference between the migration velocity of the band profile of the enantiomers to increase, which facilitates separation.^{36,37}

For the scheme 2, the mobile phase composition and flow rate in CCh were set at the same optimal levels as for the scheme 1: $\varphi_{CCh} = 10\%$ and $Q_{CCh} = 4 \text{ mL min}^{-1}$. Calculations were carried out for different values of $ee_{S,F}$; $ee_{S,F} = 0, 30, 50,$ and 70% . Additionally, the demand for ee_S of the $FICCh$ fraction transferred between CCh and ACh was incrementally changed ($ee_{S,FICCh}$ Table 2). The algorithm used for the scheme 1 (Figure 10) was also applied for these calculations. The decision variables used to maximize Pr were: L_d , Q_{ACh} and $ee_{S,FICCh}$. The constraints for $Y \geq 90\%$, $Pu \geq 99\%$, $\Delta t_{c,ACh-CCh} < \delta$ and for establishment of CSS were set the same as those used for the scheme 1. The calculations were initialized with L_d corresponding to maximum Pr on the Pareto plot for the standalone CCh at the specified $ee_{S,F}$. The results obtained with respect to Pr , Y and $m_{c,prod}$ are reported in Table 2. It is evident that for each $ee_{S,F}$, the $ee_{S,FICCh}$ level can be optimized with respect to Pr and $m_{t,prod}$. For example, for racemate and mixtures with $ee_{S,F} = 30\%$, the

Table 1. Separation Performance of ACh-CCh for the Scheme 1 and Standalone CCh; Maximum Pr was Achieved at $Y \geq 99\%$

feed $ee_{S,F}\%$	ACh-CCh, scheme 1		standalone CCh	
	$Pr_{total} = Pr_{ACh} \text{ g L}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$	$m_{t,prod}/V_{col} \text{ g L}^{-1}$	$Pr_{CCh} \text{ g L}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$	$m_{t,prod}/V_{col} \text{ g L}^{-1}$
30	34.5	0.9	32.4	0.3
50	51.0	1.2	29.1	0.3
70	94.6	2.3	47.1	0.5
85	160	4.0	65.1	0.7

Table 2. Separation Performance of ACh-CCh and the Standalone CCh and for Scheme 2, Maximum Pr was Achieved at $Y = 90\%$

feed $ee_{S,F}\%$	ACh-CCh, scheme 2			standalone CCh	
	$ee_{S,FICCh}\%$	$Pr_{total} = Pr_{ACh} \text{ G L}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$	$m_{t,prod}/V_{col} \text{ g L}^{-1}$	$Pr_{CCh} \text{ g L}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$	$m_{t,prod}/V_{col} \text{ g L}^{-1}$
0	30	18.9	0.6	35.6	0.4
	50 ^a	28.3	0.6		
	70	29.7	0.5		
	90	28.8	0.4		
30	50 ^a	44.6	1.1	48.5	0.6
	70	43.3	0.8		
	90	42.6	0.6		
50	70 ^a	43.9	0.8	57.0	0.7
	90	39.6	0.6		
70	90 ^a	69.4	1.2	68.2	0.8

^aPreferable value with respect to Pr and $m_{t,prod}$.

Table 3. Separation Performance of the Standalone CCh and the Standalone ACh, Maximum Pr Achieved at $Y \geq 65\%$ ($Q = 8 \text{ mL min}^{-1}$)

feed $ee_{S,F}\%$	standalone CCh		standalone ACh	
	$Pr_{total} = Pr_{CCh} \text{ g L}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$	$m_{t,prod}/V_{col} \text{ g L}^{-1}$	$Pr_{total} = Pr_{ACh} \text{ g L}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$	$m_{t,prod}/V_{col} \text{ g L}^{-1}$
90	140.4	2.4	186.8	1.3

$ee_{S,FICCh}$ level of 50% is favorable for the process efficiency (Table 2). Regardless of the $ee_{S,F}$ level, maximum Pr was achieved at the minimum required yield $Y = 90\%$.

The benefit of using ACh-CCh in the scheme 2 also increased with increasing $ee_{S,F}$. For the racemic mixture, whose separation was only possible in this flowsheet scheme, the mass of the pure product obtained in a single chromatographic cycle was 1.5 times higher in ACh-CCh than in the standalone CCh. The productivity in ACh-CCh was, however, lower. As mentioned above, it stemmed from the necessity of synchronization of chromatographic cycle times for both columns. For $ee_{S,F} = 30\%$, the scheme 2 performed better but with a lower yield ($Y = 90\%$) compared to the scheme 1 at the optimal separation conditions ($Y = 99\%$). For $ee_{S,F} \geq 50\%$ the scheme 1 performed better than the scheme 2. The increase in $ee_{S,F}$ caused that a fraction of pure target enantiomer withdrawn from the ACh column (the product) increased, which reduced the amount of mass to be processed in the CCh column. It caused an improvement in the separation performance for the scheme 1.

Finally, the separation performance of a highly enriched mixture $ee_{S,F} = 90\%$ was evaluated for both the standalone CCh and ACh (Table 3). The comparison was made for Y corresponding to the maximum productivity achieved in ACh, which was $Y = 65\%$. Although the standalone ACh required more cycles to produce a proper mass of the product, it could be operated at a higher productivity and significantly lower material (adsorbent) cost compared to the standalone CCh. It is evident in this case ACh could completely replace CCh.

The values given in Tables 1, 2, and 3 are specific for the separation case studied; the optimal configuration and optimal operating variables would depend on the adsorption properties.

However, the approach developed for process design is general and can be adopted for any enantiomeric mixture exhibiting the SDE effect.

5. CONCLUSIONS

In this study, a concept for partial or complete replacement of cost-consuming chiral chromatography (CCh) by achiral chromatography (ACh) for the separation of enantiomers exhibiting the SDE effect was presented. In this concept, ACh can be used instead of CCh in the separation of enantiomeric mixtures highly enriched with the target enantiomer, while the ACh-CCh coupling can be used for mixtures with a low or moderate enrichment level. A procedure was developed for the design and optimization of the separation in both standalone operations as well as in the coupled process. The procedure consisted of the formulation of the dynamic model for both the standalone ACh and the CCh and the determination of the model parameters along with their dependencies on operating variables, including the column loading density, the flow rate, and the composition of the mobile phase, which were quantified on the basis of experimental band profiles. The procedure was tested for a model mixture of methyl *p*-tolyl sulfoxide, in which *S*-methyl *p*-tolyl sulfoxide was the target enantiomer. Separation productivity and yield for the target enantiomer were evaluated as functions of the operating variables with the aid of Pareto plots. In the subsequent step, the performance of two different flowsheet schemes of the coupled process was assessed, with the feed being loaded into the ACh column or into the CCh column. The former was applicable only for $ee_S > 0$, while the latter was applicable for any ee_S of the feed mixtures.

The maximum productivity achievable in the ACh-CCh coupling and the mass of the product acquired in the single chromatographic cycle were compared with those achieved for the standalone CCh. For racemic mixtures, the productivity of the coupled process was lower than that of the standalone CCh, which resulted from the necessity of synchronizing the separation in both columns. However, the product mass per separation cycle in ACh-CCh was 1.5 higher than in the standalone CCh. It allowed for a reduction in the number of cycles in the ACh-CCh coupling compared to that in the standalone CCh, which can reduce the consumption of expensive CSP. For feed mixtures with $ee_{S,F} \geq 30\%$, the coupled ACh-CCh process outperformed the standalone CCh with respect to both productivity and product mass per cycle. This benefit was enhanced with increasing $ee_{S,F}$, for example, for $ee_{S,F} = 70\%$ the productivity in ACh-CCh was twice higher than in the standalone CCh and the mass of the product per cycle was four times higher. For mixtures with very high $ee_{S,F}$, it was recommended to use standalone ACh instead of CCh, which could significantly reduce the separation costs. The additional advantage of ACh is that the target enantiomer always elutes before the undesired one, which allows utilization of the displacement effect to concentrate the product fraction. In CCh, the elution order depends on the specificity of the chiral compound and CSP. Although the performance indicators reported are specific for the case study considered, the design concept and the experimental procedure can be generalized for any chiral compound possessing SDE-phoric groups. Moreover, further improvement in the process performance could be achieved by implementing a continuous mode in the coupled process. A study on this issue is underway.

■ ASSOCIATED CONTENT

SI Supporting Information

The Supporting Information is available free of charge at <https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acs.iecr.5c00412>.

Velocity and retention dependence of the apparent dispersion coefficient; courses of the van Deemter curves for achiral and chiral chromatography; model verification for different loading conditions and ee_S of enantiomeric mixtures; empirical functional dependencies of the isotherm coefficients for achiral and chiral chromatography; Pareto plots for the verification of mobile phase velocity effect on the optimum of modifier concentration (PDF)

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Notes

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